

Determination of extent of antibiotic resistance bacteria in wastewater and removal of antibiotics using UV-H₂O₂ process

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Abstract : Emerging contaminants (ECs), like antibiotics in wastewater has drawn much attention in recent years. Several studies reported development of antibiotics resistant pathogenic strains due to long-term exposure of various antibiotics. The present studies show that the EC₅₀ (measure of compound's 50% inhibition on bacterial growth) for the antibiotics on *E. coli* is on higher magnitude than environmentally significant concentrations. While checking for EC₅₀ for *E. coli* against fluoroquinolone antibiotics (ciprofloxacin (CIP) and ofloxacin (OFL) in different municipal and hospital wastewater, the observed values were that *E. coli* isolated from municipal wastewater exhibits 4 to 11 times fold resistance whereas in case of hospital wastewater *E. coli* exhibits around 14 to 30 times fold resistance. In the degradation study of antibiotics, the results exhibit direct photolysis was found to be very slow compare to UV-H₂O₂ process in degrading the antibiotics, only 17% for CIP and 12% for OFL was observed through direct photolysis. Whereas, for the UV-H₂O₂ process, more than 80% transformation of antibiotics was achieved with peroxide dose of 5 mol H₂O₂/mol antibiotics within 60 min at pH 7.

Keywords : Antibiotics, *E. coli*, Ciprofloxacin, Ofloxacin, UV, UV-H₂O₂.

I. Introduction

Over the past decades the occurrence, fate, and risks of residual antibiotics in the environment have become apparent as an emerging concern¹. Though release of these contaminants into the environment has been occurring for quite some time, but methods for their detection at environmentally-relevant concentrations have only recently become available. Several recent studies on emerging contaminants (ECs) like antibiotics are directed towards understanding their environmental fate due to the associated hazards². Antibiotics are chemical substances which have capability to deactivate or kill other microorganism, generally infection causing bacteria; even they are very active in a very low concentration³. On the basis of chemical structure of antibiotics, they can be classified into different classes like β -lactam : amoxicillin and Penicillin G; fluoro-

quinolone : Ciprofloxacin and Ofloxacin; Macrolide : azithromycin; sulfonamide : Sulfadoxine; and tetracycline : tetracycline. Now a day's certain serious side effects of antibiotics have been observed due to emergence of antibiotic resistance bacteria. The wide application of antibiotics in human and veterinary medicine has led to a large-scale dissemination of bacteria resistance to antibiotics in the environment. This leads to an increase in the percentage participation of antibiotic resistant bacteria in various environments causing problems in therapy by selecting resistant bacteria. An international level of investigation made by southern Austria in sewage, sludge and receiving waters from three different STP said that a total 767 *E. coli* were isolated and tested regarding their resistance to 24 different antibiotics. The highest resistance rates were found in *E. coli* strains of a STP which treats hospital sewage⁴. A national level

research on resistance of antimicrobial bacteria, the prevalence of antibiotic resistant serotypes of *E. coli* in Cochin estuary, India revealed that more than 53.33% of the isolates were multiple antibiotics resistant⁵. Antibiotics, their metabolites and resistant bacteria are excreted with urine and faeces to the wastewater, especially in to hospital sewage; these sewages possess multiple antibiotic resistances genes, as a physiological component of the micro-biota, called multiple resistance bacteria (MAR). The persistence of resistance bacteria due to unnecessary exposures of antibiotics in the aquatic environment has since become a serious public health concern⁶.

Since the elimination of antibiotics in conventional wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) is incomplete and unnecessary exposure of aquatic environmental micro-biota to antibiotics has become a serious environmental concern. Several methods have been designed through many works such as, adsorption using activated carbon⁷, ozonation in combination with different filtering techniques⁸, photocatalytic removal from aqueous solution using nanoparticles⁹, and photo Fenton oxidation method for elimination of CIP and OFL¹⁰. Over the last few years advance oxidation process using UV-H₂O₂ have been demonstrated to be very effective for removal of the pharmaceuticals compounds¹¹. In the UV-H₂O₂ process, hydrogen peroxide absorbs UV light and undergoes rapid decomposition to form hydroxyl radicals, which corresponds to the low-pressure UV lamps used in a majority of wastewater treatment plants for disinfection¹². Therefore, the objectives in the present study are (i) determination the EC₅₀ of *E. coli* strains isolated from wastewater against selected antibiotics and (ii) degradation study of antibiotics using UV-H₂O₂ process in aqueous solution.

II. Materials and methods

A. Reagents

Ciprofloxacin (C₁₇H₁₈FN₃O₃, 99.5%) and Ofloxacin (C₁₈H₂₀FN₃O₄, 99.5%) antibiotics were purchased from Sigma Aldrich in the form of injection. Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30%), hydrochloric acid (HCl, 37%), and sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 99%) pellets were purchased from Merck. All work-

ing stock solution was prepared in deionized water.

B. Wastewater sample collection and processing

Wastewater samples were collected from two (2) different municipal and three (3) different hospital sewers in the month of September, 2016 in the Howrah Municipality, West Bengal. Municipal wastewater was collected from two different sewer drains termed as MWW1, and MWW2, respectively. Hospital wastewaters were collected from three different sewer drains, termed as HWW1, HWW2 and HWW3. Sample were collected from sewer drains in samples bottles and carried to the laboratory. Then the collected samples were filtered using commercial filter paper followed by Whatman 42 filter paper to remove the most of the suspended impurities and stored the samples at 4°C until further use.

C. Instruments

A high precision electrical balance (Afcoset ER-182) was used for weighing. Digital pH meter (Orion 420A+, Thermo) was used for pH measurements. A spectrophotometer (single beam spectrophotometer 117, Systronics) was used for absorbance measurement. UV Reactor (M/s. Lab Tree) was used for degradation of antibiotics (CIP and OFL).

D. Biological safety cabinet

The bio-assay was conduct using biological safety cabinet. It is an enclosed, ventilated laboratory work space for safely working with pathogens contaminated materials. The work area of the biological safety cabinet is bathed with HEPA-filtered unidirectional (laminar) flow ISO 5/Class 100 air to protect the product and personnel. This filter removes organisms and particulates 0.3 micron in size with an efficiency of 99.99%. Approximately 70% of the air from each cycle is recirculates through the supply HEPA filter.

E. UV reactor

Direct photolysis and advanced oxidation experiments were conducted using a batch UV reactor (M/s. Lab Tree) system that emits monochromatic light at 253.7 nm. The reactor is comprised of eight UV bulbs, fitted inside a metal enclosure with a highly polished stainless-steel reflector. The photon flux of

the UV reactor was determined by Ferrioxalate actinometry¹³. The photon flux was 1.81×10^{-05} Einstein/min/100 mL.

F. Analytical method

A UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Systronics UV-Vis 117) was used with 1 cm optical path length quartz cells for all absorbance measurements. Initially a standard solution of 10 mg/L were prepared for CIP and OFL individually and scan both the sample for wavelength range of 200–900 nm, to get the optimum wavelength for particular species. Then a series of solution prepared in the concentration range of 0–15 mg/L for CIP and OFL and measure the absorbance at optimum wavelength, which was measured previously through scanning. A standard calibration curve was prepared between the concentrations and absorbance. Then from the calibration curve we can directly find the concentration of an unknown sample of antibiotics.

G. Experimental studies

G.1. To detect the extent of antibiotic resistant bacteria in the wastewater

Wastewater samples were collected in sterilized polyethylene containers from municipal and hospital sewers/drains of different places from Howrah and Kolkata city. The samples were carried to the laboratory and stored at 4°C until further use. The collected wastewater samples were filtered using commercial filter papers, followed by Whatman 42 filter paper to remove majority of suspended solids. Thereafter, the *E. coli* were isolated from the wastewaters using standard protocol by selective MUG agar media¹⁴. First make the standard solution of MUG agar (2.8 g in 100 ml distilled water) and sterilized the solution; after being cooled at room temperature pour 10 ml of solution into sterilized Petridis and when the solution comes into solid state poured 200–300 µL wastewater sample and spread it all over the solid MUG agar surface and sealed it properly. Then placed it 24 h of incubation at 37°C; colonies were identified. Susceptibility testing of the selected antibiotics was performed by broth dilution method (60%). Inoculums for susceptibility testing was prepared by dissolving a loopful of each bacterial isolate in 0.9

sterile saline solutions (lactose broth; standard solutions were prepared by dissolving 1.3 g in 100 ml distilled water) and placed it 24 h of incubation at 37°C; then the turbidity was measured. The turbidity was compared with 0.5 McFarland standard solutions¹⁵. Thereafter, the bio-assay was performed using 96 well plates. The inoculums (100 µL) and antibiotic standards (100 µL) were added to 96 well plates and incubated for 24 h at 35°C. Microplates were generally constructed as;

NEG	NEG	NEG	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
NEG	NEG	NEG	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
NEG	NEG	NEG	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
			10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
			10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	POS	POS	POS
19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	POS	POS	POS
19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	POS	POS	POS

NEG = (100 µL DI + 100 µL lactose broth)
 POS = (100 µL DI + 100 µL inoculum)

In the test plates first two rows samples were run in duplicate and in the rest samples were run in triplicate, including three positive and negative growth controls. After the incubation period, microplates were manually aspirated, shaken in the microplate reader and the optical density at 625 nm was recorded for each well. Mean measurements were used for analysis. Optical density was converted to inhibition of *E. coli* growth using equation¹⁶;

$$I(\%) = \left(\frac{OD_{625,POS} - OD_{625,EXP}}{OD_{625,POS} - OD_{625,NEG}} \right) \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

In eq. (1) 'I' is the percentage inhibition; OD₆₂₅ is the optical density at 625 nm of positive growth control, negative growth control and experimental samples, respectively. Inhibition data was fit to the Hill equation;

$$I(\%) = I_{\min} + \frac{I_{\max} - I_{\min}}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{EC_{50}}{C} \right)^H \right]} \quad (2)$$

In eq. (2) I_{\max} is the maximum inhibition, I_{\min} is the

minimum inhibition, EC_{50} is the antibiotic concentration that results in 50% inhibition of *E. coli* growth, C is the antibiotic concentration in the well, H is the Hill slope.

G.2. To investigate UV-H₂O₂ AOP in reduction of antibiotic load from wastewater

Direct photolysis and advanced oxidation experiments were conducted using batch UV reactor. All experiments were conducted using 100 mL of antibiotics bearing wastewater and 10 mM phosphate buffer at $27(\pm 2)^{\circ}C$. The samples of direct photolysis were kept in a quartz beaker with upper and lower surface been covered and irradiated for 1 h. The samples were taken at every 15 min interval analyzed for percentage of degradation of antibiotic concentration.

For UV-H₂O₂ process, the H₂O₂ doses were set as molar ratio of H₂O₂ to antibiotics. To investigate the effect of H₂O₂ dose on the efficiency of degradation of CIP and OFL, experiments were performed under different H₂O₂ dose (from molar ratio 1 to 15 at regular interval) and optimum efficiency were achieved at molar ratio 5 (mol of H₂O₂/mol of antibiotics) and the pH of the solution was 7 ± 0.1 .

III. Results and discussion

A. Studying antibiotic resistance of the isolated species by serial dilution technique

A.1. Determination of EC_{50} for pure *E. coli* against Ciprofloxacin and Ofloxacin

To determine the extent of antibiotics resistance of *E. coli* bacteria isolated from different wastewater, first of all we have investigated the EC_{50} value of pure *E. coli*; with which we compare the EC_{50} value of *E. coli* isolated from wastewater. The pure *E. coli* strains were collected from Post Graduate Institute of Medical Science Research located near to Sealdah station. The *E. coli* strains were carried to laboratory with ice boxes and then stored at $4^{\circ}C$ until further use.

An inoculum was prepared by dissolving a loopful of pure *E. coli* bacterial in lactose broth and the turbidity was adjusted at 0.5 McFarland standard solutions. The obtained suspension was used for CIP

and OFL antibiotic susceptibility testing through serial dilution method by making a bioassay with 96 well micro-plates. Then the micro-plates were incubated for 24 h at $35^{\circ}C$. After incubation, the optical density of the samples was measured and growth inhibition percentages were calculated. Thereby EC_{50} and MIC was determined. EC_{50} value was observed of pure *E. coli* in CIP was $25 \mu\text{g/L}$ as shown in Fig. 1. While checking the inhibition of pure *E. coli* in terms of EC_{50} with serial dilution technique against OFL it's found that EC_{50} was only $20 \mu\text{g/L}$. The

Fig. 1. Inhibition pattern of pure *E. coli* in Ciprofloxacin.

Fig. 2. Inhibition pattern of pure *E. coli* in Ofloxacin.

inhibition patterns of *E. coli* are shown in Fig. 2.

A.2. Determination of EC_{50} for *E. coli* collected from wastewater against CIP and OFL

The EC_{50} values of *E. coli* isolated from wastewaters tested against CIP and OFL, details results are given in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

The EC_{50} values of pure *E. coli* obtained through experiment against CIP and OFL are in good agreement with the standards as recommended by WHO.

Table 1. Summary of *E. coli* resistance isolated from wastewater tested against CIP

Place	EC ₅₀ (µg/L)	Fold resistance
Pure	25	–
MWW1	100	4
MWW2	190	8
HWW1	350	14
HWW2	718	29
HWW3	741	30

Table 2. Summary of *E. coli* resistance isolated from wastewater tested against OFL

Place	EC ₅₀ (µg/L)	Fold resistance
Pure	20	–
MWW1	100	5
MWW2	216	11
HWW1	413	21
HWW2	536	27
HWW3	552	28

This shows that that the experimental values for pure *E. coli* were within the standard range. An investigation made by Sukumaran on percentage of antibiotic resistance of *E. coli* strains isolated from Cochin estuary, India. Results shows that most of the *E. coli* strains were found to be resistant to ampicillin (65.33%) followed by nalidixic acid (37.33%), tetracycline (33.33%), cotrimoxazole (17%), trimethoprim (17%), kanamycin (14%), and ciprofloxacin (12%). The least resistance was detected against ceftriaxone (5.33%), streptomycin (4%), chloramphenicol (2.66%), gentamicin (2.66%), and amikacin (1.33%)¹⁷.

So, in the overall study of the inhibition pattern of *E. coli* isolated from wastewaters; the results clearly indicate that the resistance generation in hospital wastewaters was relatively very high than in municipal wastewaters, that means residual antibiotics has a influencing effect in resistance generation.

B. Studying advance oxidation process

To evaluate the efficiency of degradation of antibiotics, experiments were done on CIP and OFL using UV and UV H₂O₂ process. Based on the dissociation constant, the speciation of antibiotics in aqueous solution can be illustrated by their distribution curve as a function of pH. The species of CIP are

[H₄CIP³⁺], [H₃CIP²⁺], [H₂CIP⁺], [HCIP⁰], [CIP⁻] and for OFL are [ofx⁺], [ofx⁰], [ofx⁻]. The specific molar absorptivity by the different species of CIP and OFL was found different under different pH. The general trend shows that molar absorptivity increases with the increase in pH and decreases with the decrease of pH. So, the experiments were carried out at neutral pH 7 and at an initial CIP/OFL concentration of 100 mg/L. The degradation of CIP and OFL was conducted by UV and UV-H₂O₂ process in batch mode. The UV wavelength was 253.7 nm in both the process and H₂O₂ dosages was 51.30 mg/L and 47.04 mg/L for CIP and OFL respectively in the UV-H₂O₂ process only. The efficiency (*E*) of degradation of Ciprofloxacin/Ofloxacin are measured by eq. (3);

$$E = \frac{C_0 - C_t}{C_0} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

where *C*₀ is the initial concentration and *C*_{*t*} is the concentration of Ciprofloxacin/Ofloxacin at time *t*, a higher value of *E* represents higher efficiency of degradation. The test results reveal that direct photolysis (UV) of CIP and OFL was not very satisfactory after 60 min; degradation was 17% for CIP and 12% for OFL. Whereas when hydrogen peroxide was added, significant efficiency was observed for both CIP and OFL. Degradation was found around 85% for CIP (Fig. 3) and around 95% (Fig. 4) for OFL after 60 min of observation. The results illus-

Fig. 3. Comparison of degradation of CIP in UV and UV-H₂O₂ process.

trated that UV-H₂O₂ process was associated with a high degree of degradation efficiency of CIP and OFL.

Further, to examine the effect of H₂O₂ dose on the efficiency of degradation of CIP and OFL, experiments were performed under different H₂O₂ dose (from molar ratio 1 to 15 at regular interval) and optimum efficiency were achieved at molar ratio 5 (mol of H₂O₂/mol of antibiotics) and the pH of the solution was 7±0.1 (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4. Comparison of degradation of OFL in UV and UV-H₂O₂ process.

Fig. 5. Variation of degradation efficiency of CIP and OFL at various H₂O₂ dose.

IV. Conclusions

In the study, the EC₅₀ for organism isolated from wastewater shows resistance value against antibiotics while compare to pure organisms. But the details result clearly showed that the EC₅₀ values determined for *E. coli* isolated from hospital wastewater was several times higher compared to *E. coli* in

municipal wastewater showing detrimental effects of persistent presence of these pharmaceutical contaminants. Direct photolysis of CIP and OFL was not very satisfactory after 60 min; degradation was 17% for CIP and 12% for OFL. Whereas when hydrogen peroxide was added, degradation was found around 85% for CIP and around 95% for OFL after 60 min of observation. The results illustrated that UV-H₂O₂ process was associated with a high degree of degradation efficiency of CIP and OFL.

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